

DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS APPLIED TO LOW POWER ONBOARD IMAGE COMPRESSION OBPDC 2022

Klepsydra Technologies

pablo.ghiglino@klepsydra.com

www.klepsydra.com

- Overview
 - Context
 - Previous work
- AI for compression
 - Research work
 - Preliminary results
- Deployment to OBC
 - Klepsydra AI
 - Past results
 - Application to AI for compression
- Conclusions and Future Work

Part 1

Overview

CONTEXT

	Type of Data	Complexity	Throughput	Lossless efficiency	Lossy efficiency	Fixed-rate Fixed quality	Commercial counterpart	Relevant Space Implementation
CCSDS 121.0-B-2	1D 32 bits	😊😊😊	😊😊😊	😊😊😊	--	Variable-rate Lossless	JPEG-LS	SHyLoC ESA IP
CCSDS 122.0-B-2	2D 16 bits(B-1) 32 bits(B-2)	😐	😊😊	😊😊	😊😊😊	Fixed-rate Coarse quality control	JPEG2000	CWICOM ASIC
CCSDS 122.1-B-1	3D 16 bits	😞/😊*	😊	😊😊	😊😊😊	Variable-rate Mechanism for rate allocation	JPEG2000	--
CCSDS 123.0-B-1	2D/3D 16 bits	😊😊	😊😊*	😊😊😊	--	Variable-rate Lossless	JPEG-LS	SHyLoC ESA IP
CCSDS 123.0-B-2	2D/3D 16 bits	😊	😐/😊*	😊😊😊	😊😊😊	Variable-rate Precise quality control	JPEG2000	--

* Quoted from OBDP2019-S04-01-ESA_Camarero_Introduction_to_CCSDS_compression_standards_and_implementations_offered_by_ESA

PREVIOUS WORK ON AI-BASED COMPRESSION

History

- In research since late 1980's (see paper references)

Principle:

- Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) with learned compression outperform state-of-the-art by 2x on bitrates of compressed images of equivalent quality.

Original

JPEG

ratio 68.4:1, PSNR 29.7 dB

B-EED

ratio 70.4:1, PSNR 30.9 dB

AI-BASED COMPRESSION FOR SENTINEL DATA

(a) Original

(b) Compressed with bmsbj2018-1

(c) Compressed with b2018

Part 2

AI for

Compression

Part 2.1

Research

NONLINEAR TRANSFORM CODING WITH NEURAL NETWORKS

- JPEG uses a Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) for **g_a** (analysis) and Inverse DCT for **g_s** (synthesis).
- Instead, one approach can be to use Artificial Neural networks for **g_a** and **g_s** .
- **g_a** and **g_s** need to be trained together, but once trained they can be run on separate machines.
- In AI, the combined DNN shown here are also referred to as AutoEncoders (since their objective is to have output = input)

Learned Image Compression: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x_q7cZviXkY

NONLINEAR TRANSFORM CODING WITH NEURAL NETWORKS

- The strategy to improve compression performance is to send additional information.
- By extending the auto-encoder into a hierarchical bayesian model using hyperprior \hat{h}_a
- Improve the entropy model by sending side information from the image.
- This is the overview of the compression model tested in this research.
- We used the two outputs of the encoder stage: y and z for validation

side information

- Learned Image Compression: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x_g7cZviXkY
- Johannes Ballé, David Minnen, Saurabh Singh, Sung Jin Hwang, and Nick Johnston. "Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior". In: International Conference on Learning Representations. 2018.

TEST ARCHITECTURE

- Johannes Ballé, David Minnen, Saurabh Singh, Sung Jin Hwang, and Nick Johnston. “Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior”. In: International Conference on Learning Representations. 2018.

OBC Performance Benchmarking

- Johannes Ballé, David Minnen, Saurabh Singh, Sung Jin Hwang, and Nick Johnston. “Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior”. In: International Conference on Learning Representations. 2018.

Part 2

Preliminary Results

THE GENERALISED DIVISIVE NORMALISATION

- The trained network contains outdated code, or layers not supported in inference engines (neither tflite or onnx).
- We constructed an equivalent network looking at the internal code.
- The conv + GDN block is shown here.
- The rest of the network is relatively simple with convolutional, ReLU, Abs and transposed convolutional layers.

Equivalent network – Analysis block

- Johannes Ballé, David Minnen, Saurabh Singh, Sung Jin Hwang, and Nick Johnston. “Variational image compression with a scale hyperprior”. In: International Conference on Learning Representations. 2018.

TEST ON SENTINEL IMAGE WITH UPDATED NETWORK

Trained network used on ESA Sentinel Mission Images

- Image compressed on “ground OBC”
- Compressed data copied to local machine (62 Kb)
- Generated image obtained from compressed data on local machine
- Trained model present on “ground OBC” and local machine

Original Image (~5.8 Mb)

Generated Image from compressed data

TEST ARCHITECTURE - PRELIM PERFORMANCE RESULTS

Reported Runtimes (as of 2018)

- On Desktop CPU : ~ 330 ms
- On mid-range gaming GPU (~20 ms)
- Network not developed with edge devices in mind

This was consistent with our own benchmarks:

- Including conversion of GDN to equivalent layers

Part 3

Deployment to OBC

Part 3.1

Klepsydra AI

LOCK-FREE AS ALTERNATIVE TO PARALLELISATION

Parallelisation

OpenMP

Pipeline

2-DIM THREADING MODEL

Deep Neural Network Structure

First dimension: pipelining

2-DIM THREADING MODEL

Second dimension: Matrix multiplication parallelisation

Input Data

Thread 1 (Core 1)

Thread 2 (Core 2)

Thread 3 (Core 3)

Output Data

2-DIM THREADING MODEL

Threading model configuration

- Low CPU
- High throughput CPU
- High latency

- Mid CPU
- Mid throughput CPU
- Mid latency

- High CPU
- Mid throughput CPU
- Low latency

Example of performance benchmarks

Part 3.2

Past Results

Klepsydra AI Test for Space Use

- Processors
 - QorIQ® Layerscape LS1046A Multicore Processor
 - ZedBoard Zynq-7000 ARM/FPGA SoC Development Board
- Operating systems:
 - Yocto Linux
 - PetaLinux
- DNN models:
 - Standard models (AlexNet, MobileNet, YOLO and SDD) and standard data.
 - ESA provided models and data (CME and Cloud Detection)

QORIQ® LAYERSCAPE LS1046A MULTICORE PROCESSOR

QorIQ® Layerscape LS1046A

Klepsydra AI Container

- **Successful installation of the following setup:**
 - LS1046 running Yocto Jethro
 - Docker Installed on LS1046
 - Container with the following:
 - Ubuntu 20.04
 - Klepsydra AI software fully supported (quantised and non-quantised)

ZedBoard

Klepsydra AI Container

- **Successful installation of the following setup:**
 - ZedBoard running PetaLinux 2019.2
 - Docker Installed on ZedBoard
 - Container with the following:
 - Ubuntu 20.04
 - Klepsydra AI software with quantised support only

PERFORMANCE RESULTS: CME ON LS1046

PERFORMANCE RESULTS: CME-Q ON LS1046

PERFORMANCE RESULTS: CME-Q ON ZEDBOARD

PERFORMANCE RESULTS: BSC ON LS1046

Part 3.3

Cloud Detection

Part 3.3

Application to AI on compression

- **Performance results carried out on**
 - x86 2-core OBC
 - Ubuntu Linux 20.02
 - Klepsydra AI v5.9

PERFORMANCE RESULTS

Part 4

Conclusions and Future work

- AI for compression can achieve 2x compressed ratio compared to other lossy compression solutions like JPEG2000
- Compression and decompression are trained together in one network that then will be separated: compression in OBC, decompression in ground.
- Performance benchmarks show that this AI networks are quite heavy. By using Klepsydra AI, execution on OBC become feasible

FUTURE WORK

A large, light gray hourglass graphic is positioned on the right side of the slide, partially overlapping the 'FUTURE WORK' header. The hourglass is oriented vertically, with the top bulb at the top and the bottom bulb at the bottom. The central neck of the hourglass is narrow, and the bulbs are wider. The graphic is semi-transparent, allowing the text behind it to be visible.

- ARM performance benchmarks: currently under research and optimisation effort.
- AI compression training for Space images to increase compressed ratio.
- Machine-to-machine AI Compression
- Compression performance benchmarks on Jetson NX

CONTACT INFORMATION

Dr Pablo Ghiglino

pablo.ghiglino@klepsydra.com

+41786931544

www.klepsydra.com

[linkedin.com/company/klepsydra-technologies](https://www.linkedin.com/company/klepsydra-technologies)